

II International Scientific Conference
Special Education and Rehabilitation – Cerebral Palsy

Book of Proceedings and Summaries

Belgrade, 2012

SPECIAL EDUCATION AND REHABILITATION – CEREBRAL PALSY

Book of Proceedings and Summaries

Publisher:

Society of Special Educators and Rehabilitators of Serbia

For publisher:

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Editors:

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Processing and printing

Planeta print, Belgrade

Cover design

Veselin Medenica

Circulation

200 copies

ISBN 978-86-84765-40-8

Review of Book of Proceedings and Abstracts "Special Education and Rehabilitation – Cerebral Palsy" was accepted by the decision (No. 72/12) of the Presidency of the Society of Special Educators and Rehabilitators of Serbia in the meeting on June 6th 2012.

II International Scientific Conference
SPECIAL EDUCATION AND REHABILITATION – CEREBRAL PALSY

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Department of Special Education and Rehabilitation of Persons with Motor Disorders

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CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

616.831-009.11(048)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference Special
Education and Rehabilitation - Cerebral Palsy
(2 ; 2012 ; Belgrade)

Book of Proceedings and Summaries / II
International Scientific Conference Special
Education and Rehabilitation - Cerebral
Palsy, Belgrade 2012. ; [organizers
University of Belgrade - Faculty of Special
Education and Rehabilitation ... [et al.] ;
editors Milan Kulic, Srecko Potic]. -
Belgrade : Society of Special Educators and
Rehabilitators of Serbia, 2012 (Beograd :
Planeta print). - 133 str. ; 24 cm

Tiraž 200. - Registar.

ISBN 978-86-84765-40-8

1. Faculty of Special Education and
Rehabilitation (Belgrade)

а) Церебрална парализа - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 193901580

THERAPEUTIC POSSIBILITIES IN THE TRETAMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Cerebral palsy (CP) describes a group of disorders of the development of movement and posture, causing activity limitation, that are attributed to non-progressive disturbances that occurred in the developing fetal or infant brain. Botulinum toxin type A (BoNT-A) is relatively recent addition to the available medical interventions for children with CP. Our research showed (41 patients) that spasticity of adductors of the hips and plantar flexors were significantly decreased two weeks, one and half months and three months after the treatment. Approximately 85% of patients achieved the expecting therapeutic goals according to Goal Attainment Scale. In combination with post-injection physiotherapy this treatment could provide long-term benefits. Functional Electrical Therapy is the clinical application of a small electric current to the intact nerves in order to trigger a muscle contraction. This contraction is then incorporated into a functional activity, for example walking, reaching etc. Our preliminary study (7 patients) showed improvement in performances of the paretic hand, better control and quality of movements. This method can serve as an additional treatment for habilitation of children with hemiparetic cerebral palsy. Therapeutic horse riding (THR) is one of the possible ways of habilitation in children with CP. As the horse walks, its center of gravity is displaced three-dimensionally with a movement very similar to the action of the human pelvis during gait. The warmth of the horse coupled with this rhythmical movement is thought to be useful in reducing abnormally high muscle tone and promoting relaxation in the rider with spastic CP. In our research (12 patients), passive range of motion (lower extremities) and muscle strength (muscles of the trunk) were significantly higher after 10 weeks of riding. Spasticity was significantly lower after the THR. The important principles in the treatment of patients with cerebral palsy are good evaluation of patients and tailored treatment for each patients.

Key words: cerebral palsy, children, therapy

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